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SYNERGIES IN MARINE APPLICATIONS OF OCEAN COLOUR, INFRARED AND SAR SATELLITE EO DATA

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REPORT

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1. Introduction

Since 1998 the Nansen Center has performed regular Earth Observation (EO) monitoring for research purposes of the North Sea, Skagerrak and southern Norwegian coastal waters (<http://www.nersc.no/HAB>), with the aim to early detect and classify potential harmful algae bloom patterns, concentration, distribution and their evolution and decay. Common for this routine monitoring activity is the characterisation of dominating ocean dynamical processes, such as frontal convergence and divergence, eddy development and rotation, occurrences of jet-like filaments, and outbreak of cold water from Kattogat. Whereas the benefit to monitoring from synergetic use of ocean colours and SST EO data have already been well documented within this activity, the eventual additional benefit from use of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) has hitherto not been systematically explored and documented for algae bloom monitoring. Such a study is highly timely in view of the successful launch of the multi-sensor Envisat satellite in March 2002.

This study therefore demonstrates the usefulness and limitations of synergetic analysis of image data from ocean colour (chlorophyll pigment concentration), sea surface temperature (SST) and SAR EO satellites for detection and classification of various bio-optical quantities and processes in ocean surface layer.

Synergetic analysis leads to improved temporal and spatial coverage, and may thus contribute to improved monitoring of natural variability of coastal zone processes. This study focuses on detection and monitoring of harmful and non-harmful massive algae bloom events, which is a major economical and health issue for the aquaculture and fisheries industries in Norway and to some extent to its neighbouring countries.

The Norwegian Space Centre has funded the study under contract JOP.8.3.3.10.02.2. Satellite EO data has been provided by the European Space Agency under ERS-2 AO project (ERS AO-3# 999311), NASA GSFC SeaWiFS users project code #55865, Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service at Plymouth Marine Laboratory and the Canadian Space Centre Radarsat ADRO project # 24567.

2. Motivation and Study Objectives

With the successful launch of Envisat in March 2002 a new opportunity for EO based marine monitoring emerged, notably the coincident and overlapping mapping and use of MERIS, AATSR and ASAR as illustrated in Figure 1. The complementary observations provided by these EO instruments are promising as already elaborated by the Nansen Center and University of Southampton through the ESA/ESTEC study “*Synergetic use of infra-red, optical and microwave remote sensing observation*”.

Figure 1: Coincident and overlapping coverage obtained from Envisat ASAR, MERIS and AATSR.

Although the Envisat satellite remained in the commissioning phase longer than anticipated and limited coincident and overlapping data has been available up to now we have been able to examine the potential usefulness of such coincident and overlapping data using other satellites. A limited examination was concentrated on the synergetic use of SeaWiFS ocean colour, AVHRR-SST, and ERS-2 SAR and RADARSAT SAR data for detection, characterisation and monitoring of algae blooms with impact on the Norwegian coastal waters in the Skagerrak and North Sea.

In so doing the specific objectives focused on:

- How the use of ocean colour data from SeaWiFS and thermal infrared imagery from NOAA AVHRR can be utilized in synergy with multi-polarization SAR data in order to improve the observations of the dominant coupled physical-biogeochemical processes in the coastal waters with frequent cloud cover.
- How improved mapping by synergetic approach can advance the interpretation and understanding of the ecosystem variability in the coastal waters.

3. Background

Ocean colour data from Earth observation satellites became, after a long period of absence, available again with the OrbView-2 satellite launched in August 1997. Since spring 1998 the Nansen Center has regularly demonstrated for research purpose in order to improve *in situ* sampling of possible algae bloom events in waters of influence of the coast of southern Norway (<http://www.nersc.no/HAB>). These activities have been funded through research projects supported by the Norwegian Space Centre, the Research Council of Norway, European Space Agency (ESA) and EC FP5. During these last years of investigations many events of massive algae blooms with a significant surface structure has been identified. Harmful blooms have been reported in 1998, 2000, 2001 and 2002 and some of these blooms have had a significant impact on the aquaculture activities in coastal Norwegian waters.

In the beginning of May 1998, a large harmful algae bloom dominated by the flagellate *Chattonella* aff. *Verruculosa* dominated the waters West of Jutland and were advected to a certain degree into coastal Swedish and Norwegian waters (e.g. Aure et al., 2000, Durand et al, 2002). This caused mass mortality of fish in aquaculture farms along the southern Norwegian coast, particular in the Flekkefjord area. Around 350 tons of salmon died, mainly mature fish. This was the first time such a large-scale bloom of *Chattonella* was registered in Europe at such high concentrations that resulted in the massive death of fish in fish-farms. A similar bloom of the same species occurred in April – May 2000, but did not reach the Norwegian coast where the main aquaculture farms are located, hence limiting the economical impact of the bloom. A third occurrence was observed in March 2001 (Pettersson et al., 2001) starting in the in the Kattegat and along the southern coast of Norway, causing severe impact on the aquaculture industry along the coast of Sørlandet westward to the Egersund district.

Commonly for these *Chattonella* blooms are that during the peak and latter stages of these blooms their vertical extension is up to the sea surface with very high cell concentrations near or at the surface. These high concentrations at the surface should give raise to surface films or slicks, which may sufficient dense to cause a damping of the surface capillary waves and accordingly give a damping backscatter signature detectable in the SAR images. Few data exist on the *in situ* quantification of this biological surfactant and its appearance at the sea surface.

The usefulness of the synergetic analysis of ERS SAR and NOAA AVHRR data was investigated in the Norwegian Continental Shelf Experiment (NORCSEX'88 and '91) and the COASTWATCH'95 experiments (Johannessen *et al.*, 1996; Johannessen *et al.*, 1997). These experiments have demonstrated the capability of these two sensors to map identically frontal zones, even if based on totally different physical phenomenon (sea surface roughness and sea surface temperature) and mapping the sea surface with two different spatial resolutions (100 m for the SAR/LRI and \square 1 km for AVHRR). These two EO sensors have also proved to be complementary for achieving a better time coverage and sampling of a particular meso-scale ocean process.

An optimal monitoring and forecasting of physical processes in coastal waters requires the possibility to characterize meso-scale ocean and atmosphere processes such as currents, eddies, fronts and wind field. The latter parameters are currently available from RADARSAT and ERS C-band SAR data as well as the Envisat ASAR since 2002. The capability of SAR images to derive information on ocean currents, fronts, eddies and surface films have been demonstrated by a large number of experiments and scientific publications (e.g., Vachon *et al.*, 1994). Likewise, sea surface temperature measured by thermal infrared sensors has shown a great capability for water masses identification and frontal zone mapping.

Within its long-term strategy program for marine applications of SAR data, the Nansen Center has designed, implemented and validated a number of SAR analysis tools and algorithms including state-of-the-art algorithm for deriving wind field, identify currents, fronts and slicks from SAR data.

This study is one of the first attempts to characterize coastal waters by an integrated multi-sensor, multi-resolution, multi-polarization approach making use of the full potential of ocean Earth

observation data. We expect that the combination of the three types of imaging sensors improve the interpretation capability of sea surface features and make it possible to study the time evolution of the ocean features (fronts, eddies, slicks, etc.) due to the improved temporal and spatial coverage. Through the regular evaluation of a long-term archive (multi-year) of various EO data sources the study will identify the practical availability of data can also be used as well as illustrate the availability of data under various environmental conditions.

The various ocean dynamical and marine environmental processes are governed by specific length and time scales. Figure 2 shows the characteristic length and time-scale of some of the major phenomenon and features relevant under ocean dynamics and marine environmental processes. Similarly, they will provide spatial coverage large enough to include the full extent of the phenomenon, and will continue monitoring for a period of time, which spans its lifetime. In the past, examination and demonstration of synergetic capabilities have been undertaken through case studies using available data sets.

Figure 2: Characteristic length and time scales of a) dynamical ocean processes and b) marine environmental processes (Miles et al, 1998).

4. Methodology

During the years 1998 to 2001 periods of “cloud free” optical (SeaWiFS) and temperature (AVHRR) data have been identified in the Nansen Center database of EO data for the North Sea, Skagerrak and southern Norwegian coastal waters (Figure 3). In addition the baseline study area includes the western coastal and shelf waters of continental Europe, covering the Dutch, German, Danish and partly Swedish waters. All these waters have a direct or indirect impact on the down stream Norwegian Coastal Current, though the prevailing ocean currents in the region. In this area regular (i.e. daily) analyses of the SeaWiFS data are performed. For this study primary focus has been made on the periods of the extensive blooms of the algae specie *Chattonella* during the period from the early spring blooms in February/March to May/June periods. Days of “cloud free” conditions over the bloom areas have been identified in the SeaWiFS and AVHRR data. Accordingly the archives of ERS-2 SAR and RADARSAT ScanSAR (also limited by the number of data granted) have been investigated in order to identify overlapping SAR mapping of the high algae bloom areas. The additional search criteria were that the wind conditions during the SAR mapping should be sufficient low to allow for observations of ocean features in the SAR data. The number of such matches of data is limited and those of high quality summarized in Table 1. The SAR data were provided respectively through and ESA ERS-2 AO project (ERS AO3 #999311) and an ADRO Radarsat project (# 24567). SeaWiFS data through a science project agreement with NASA GSFC and near real time provision by Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service at Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

Figure 3: The coverage of the regular area of SeaWiFS and AVHRR data collected and analyzed by the Nansen Center based on EO data provision from the Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service at Plymouth Marine Laboratory. The 200 meters depth contour is indicated, which often is correlated with the extension of the Norwegian Coastal Current.

This study consists of the following tasks:

1. Review the archives of high quality (in terms of cloud cover and data availability) EO data from the two main optical and infrared EO sensors, in order to identify cloud free high quality images during algae bloom events.
2. Review SAR data quick-looks for identified periods and order SAR with relevant surface signatures during the major bloom events.
3. Identification of fronts, current shear and eddies as mapped in the ocean colour, SST and SAR data.
4. Analysis of ocean colour data for mapping of algae bloom events, collocated with information from ERS-2 and RADARSAT SAR as well as AVHRR-SST data.
5. Studies of the effects of SAR polarization on surface feature detection will be investigated by comparison of RADARSAT ScanSAR data and ERS-2 SAR data.

Processing and analysis of the SeaWiFS, AVHRR, ERS-2 SAR and RADARSAT SAR data have been performed for a study area covering the west Jutland current, across the Skagerrak and along the southwest coast of Norway. The data processing includes radiometric and geometric corrections, use of algorithms to derive wind vectors, estimate surface temperature, chlorophyll, and supervised and manual identification of currents, fronts, eddies, upwelling and surface slicks.

SeaWiFS ocean colour data has been atmospherically corrected using the standard NASA SeaDAS processing package (various versions, including version 3.0, applied). This includes atmospheric correction of the data before the retrieval of the chlorophyll pigment concentrations. These methods have been developed for waters of different optical properties than the areas of investigations and accordingly the errors in the retrieved parameters can be very large. Still, the retrieved values and gradients are fairly consistent with the actual observed conditions during this type of algal bloom events. More optimised methods for the North Sea and Skagerrak waters are under validation.

AVHRR sea surface temperature (SST) has been analyzed for identification of ocean front locations and identification and tracking of water masses of various origins.

The backscatter values ERS-2 and RADARSAT ScanSAR images have been processed in order to enhance the surface signal over the sea. The ERS SAR precision images (PRI) used in the study has been calibrated using software from ESA ESRIN (<http://earth.esa.int/services/best/>). The full resolution scenes have then been reduced to a pixel size of 100m x 100m by averaging. The SAR LRI data cannot be calibrated, but are used for visual inspection and comparison of surface phenomenon and features. The SAR images are analyzed to detect current fronts and surface films for potential connection with high algae concentrations at or near the surface as resolved in the chlorophyll-*a* pigment concentration product from SeaWiFS data.

The potential of multi-polarization analysis has been evaluated by simultaneous utilization of ERS C-band VV and RADARSAT C-band HH SAR data. VV polarization accounts for the strongest signal and is useful for wind measurements, while HH polarization is expected to be more sensitive for monitoring surface slicks. Thus, a comparison of the observed sea surface signature patterns has been performed, and the possibility for these sensors to complement each other in the observations of the surface expression of algae bloom events.

5. Results

Useful, high quality and overlapping near synoptic EO data during major algae blooms events (mainly less than ± 12 hrs. time difference between observations - actually 2 to 9 hrs.) has been identified for one to four days each year during the major bloom events in the four years period from 1998-2001. Situations when only one or two of the sensors available have also been examined, however they are excluded from this report. An overview of the data collected and presented in this report is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of the selected EO data giving date, time, platform and sensor and data type.

Case #	Date	Time (UTC)	EO Sensor (data type)
I	13 May 1998	05:51	RSAT ScanSAR
		12:41	SeaWiFS
	14 May 1998	11:48	SeaWiFS
I B	15 May 1998	12:32	SeaWiFS
		12:30	AVHRR SST
		10:33	ERS-2 SAR (5*PRI)
II	3 May 2000	XX:XX	ERS-2 SAR (LRI)
	4 May 2000	05:54	AVHRR SST
		12:19	SeaWiFS
		21:30	ERS-2 SAR (LRI)
	5 May 2000	04:42	AVHRR SST
II B	12 May 2000	06:00	RSAT ScanSAR
		11:34	SeaWiFS
		14:55	AVHRR SST
III	27 March 2001	11:43	SeaWiFS
		10:27	ERS-2 SAR (4*PRI)
IV	8 May 2001	21:33	ERS-2 SAR (5*PRI)
	9 May 2001	06:18	AVHRR SST
		12:51	SeaWiFS
IV B	15 May 2001	12:13	SeaWiFS
		21:13	ERS-2 SAR (PRI)
V	19 May 1999	06:49	AVHRR SST
		12:12	SeaWiFS
		22:03	ERS-2 SAR (PRI)

5.1 Data Interpretation and Analysis

Algae bloom events are identified in the processed chlorophyll-a pigment concentration images based on SeaWiFS data, using the standard SeaDAS processing tool (various versions up to v3.0 are used). The chlorophyll concentration is estimated from the amount of algae pigments in the upper meters of the water column (pending on the transparency of the water). Hence, algae blooms with a high biomass near the surface will become more visible in the ocean colour data than those with a subsurface peak. This is also one element to be taken into consideration in synergy studies involving SAR data that maps the surface expression of e.g. biological film or surfactants at the ocean surface.

Additionally, true colour composite images are generated and used to characterise the water reflection (a Red-Green-Blue composite of the reflectance in respectively 555, 490 and 412 nm). These data are used to improve the interpretation of the causes and variability in the pigment concentration products as defined above. In order to confirm and identify the algal blooms *in situ* sampling and observations were performed primarily through observations by Institute of Marine Research and Directorate of Fisheries. Despite the uncertainty in the absolute accuracy of SeaWiFS derived parameters, these data has proven to provide useful information on the initiation, development, locations and gradients in the bloom parameters.

Synoptic sea surface temperature (SST) data from NOAA AVHRR are generated and used to characterize water masses as well as current extent and gradients in the coastal current and further offshore. Taking the difference between the SST and the air temperature the stability of the atmospheric boundary layer can be assessed.

Interpretation of SAR mapping of the surface backscatter is closely related to wind conditions and air-sea temperature differences (boundary layer stability). Six hourly meteorological analyses from ECMWF has been obtained and plotted to provide independent information on the wind and temperature conditions. In general the ocean signature in SAR images can be classified into two different situations: Wind speed greater than 8-10 m/s where oceanographic induced surface features vanish in the SAR images and wind speed less than 8-10 m/s under which ocean features are detectable. In the first case the wind waves are dominant over other types of ocean surface signatures and the only type of signatures that are seen are wind related, such as; lee effects, atmospheric roll vortices, Langmuir cells. One such case is the March 2001-case (III) where we used the CMOD-IFR2 transfer-function to retrieve the wind vectors from the ERS SAR images from the 27th March.

In the second case surface currents and slicks may be dominant over the wind waves. Surface slicks can originate from river discharge, i.e. from land, or be produced by algae activity. These are oily substances and therefore floats to the surface and tend to dampen the short gravity and capillary waves responsible for the radar return. This results in low radar backscatter in the SAR images. However, also calm weather conditions (wind speed ≤ 2 m/s) and stable near surface conditions ($T_{\text{air}} > T_{\text{sea}}$) gives low radar return and this cannot always be distinguished from surface slicks.

Current fronts and in particular current convergence and shear zones, are seen in the boundary between two water masses (e.g. the Norwegian Coastal Current and the North-Atlantic current). In addition, current features can originate from internal waves, eddies and interaction with bottom topography. Surface eddies can often be clearly delineated by surfactants as they are drawn into shapes and patterns by the differences in the water movement.

5.1.1 Case I: *Chattonella* bloom west Jutland - May 1998

At the beginning of May 1998, a large harmful algae bloom dominated by the flagellate *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa*, probably in combination with a small amount of *Heterosigma akashiwo*, caused mass mortality of fish in farms in the Farsund and Flekkefjord area. Around 350 tonnes of salmon died, mainly mature fish. This was the first time *Chattonella* was registered in Europe, and also the first time it had appeared in such high concentrations, which resulted in the massive death of aquacultured fish. The algae specie was later observed at the western coast of Sweden, and affected the whole area of Skagerrak by the beginning of May (see Figure 4). Later high concentrations were reported along the west and northern coast of Jutland, resulting in the death of garfish, herring and sand eel. The high concentrations of *Chattonella* in the Skagerrak and along the western coast of Jutland were found in water, which contained unusually high concentrations of nutrients during this time of the year. Large amounts of anthropogenic nitrate from the southern part of the North Sea probably stimulated the extreme growth of the algae bloom together with favourable sun conditions. The bloom had its maximum extension during mid-May and culminated towards the last week of the month. Through this period several high quality SeaWiFS ocean colour EO images have been available and analysed (Figure 4) together with ERS SAR and AVHRR SST (Figure 6).

Figure 4. Chlorophyll pigment concentration product from SeaWiFS over the North Sea and the Skagerrak, on (a) May 13, (b) May 15, (c) May 17, 1998. The sea surface temperature (SST) for the same dates are shown in (d)-(e). The SST data for the 13th are lacking. The time series shows the increases and decay of a *Chattonella* spp. bloom, along the west coast of Jutland, Denmark.

Blue/purple indicates low pigment; red indicates high pigment.

© Orbital Imaging Corps / NASA SeaWiFS project. Courtesy: Steve Groom, RSDAS/PML.

During this HAB event additional ERS and Radarsat SAR data were available and has been used in the synergy analysis together with meteorological boundary layer information from ECMWF (Figure 7 and Figure 8).

The AVHRR SST image of May 15th in the western Skagerrak is partly contaminated by clouds and aircraft curtails, which are interfering and masking some of the surface gradients in the SST (Figure 6). The exact interpretation on the image is accordingly difficult, however examination of the same data source obtained on the 17th support the following interpretation.

The Norwegian coastal water is colder than the offshore Skagerrak water in the area south of Kristiansand. A tongue of warm waters is breaking out through the central part of Skagerrak and extending up along the west coast of Jæren. The temperature of these water masses is at a similar level to the surface water in the central Skagerrak gyre. In the SeaWiFS ocean colour data an offshore decreasing gradient (off-shore values are 20-50% of the coastal concentrations) in the chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentrations are observed. In the central Skagerrak the inflow of colder and significantly less chlorophyll-rich (purple colour in Chl-a pigment concentration with typical values of 2-5% of the coastal water concentrations) water of Atlantic origin occurs. This inflow of waters of Atlantic origin through the North Sea is to a very large extent steered by the topography of the Norwegian Trench. This interpretation reveals that SST and Chl-a satellite based data provide similar and complementary information on water masses and their biological and geophysical conditions as well as the ocean circulation pattern. However, the expressions of this ocean circulation pattern are resolved by different strength (contrasts) in the biological Chl-a concentration and in the SST expression of the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC).

On the 15th May the air temperature from the ECMWF reanalysis data is about 11°C in this area and the SST data from AVHRR are about 1°C warmer (see Figure 4 and Figure 8). The wind speed and atmospheric boundary layer stability i.e. the temperature difference between the water surface and the air temperature, should therefore cause a higher normalised radar cross section (NRCS) along the coast of Norway than for the colder water mass further off-shore due to turbulence created by more unstable near-surface conditions (Figure 6) which is what is observed in the ERS SAR image of the 15th. The current system in the area off Lista as mapped in the SST data from the 17th is well confirmed with the model simulations for both the 15th and 17th using Nansen Center HYCOM (Figure 5), with a even more pronounced signature in the SST on the 17th.

Figure 5: HYCOM model simulations of the ocean currents and SST on respectively the 15th and 17th May, 1998.

Figure 6: The AVHRR SST, ERS SAR image and SeaWiFS Chl-a distribution for the area in western Skagerrak and Jutland current on May 15th. The SAR coverage area is superimposed.

Figure 7: To the upper right is shown the SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a pigment data from the 13th, 14th and 15th during the *Chattonella* bloom west of Jutland. ECMWF surface wind speed and direction are plotted for the 15th at noon (center upper panel). The three plots of temperature, wind speed and wind direction are obtained at the locations 1-3 indicated in the contour plot of the wind field. The wind speed in this figure ranges from 0-7m/s. Due to higher wind on the 13th (at Radarsat passage) than on the 15th at ERS-2 passage, more ocean features are observed in the ERS-2 images.

Figure 8: ECMWF reanalysis of wind speed for the mornings of May 13th (06 UTC – close to Radarsat passage), 14th (12 UTC) and 15th (12 UTC – close to ERS SAR passage).

The series of data during 13-15th May 1998 illustrates the importance of the wind speed being in the right range when studying ocean features in SAR images (Figure 7). The wind during this period was easterly, turning northward in Skagerrak. The wind speeds in Skagerrak northwest of Jutland were 7 m/s on the morning of the 13th (RADARSAT), decreasing to 4,5 m/s on the 14th and further decreasing to 2 m/s on the 15th at noon (ERS) (see Figure 7). Accordingly the Radarsat image obtained on the 13th shows the clear signatures of wind streaks indicating easterly wind in agreement with the ECMWF data (Figure 7). Cloud rows aligned with the wind direction offshore from Jutland are furthermore observed in the SeaWiFS image from the 14th. The northernmost ERS-2 SAR scene from the 15th on the other hand are in the region of 2m/s wind speed and show very clear signatures of ocean fronts, eddies and surface slicks, except for the near shore area, which has been discussed above.

Several eddies and surface slick signatures observed in the SAR image are co-located with eddies/fronts in the SeaWiFS images and the regions of high pigment concentrations as well as in

the gradient areas in the SST. In particular west of Jutland the *Chattonella* bloom reached extremely high concentrations with a profound surface accumulation of the algae cells. This indicates that the bloom became so dense at the surface that it caused enough surfactants to damp out the capillary waves and being visible in the SAR image under moderate to low wind speeds, such as observed on the 15th. However, the low backscatter SAR signatures (ERS data collected two hours prior to the SeaWiFS and AVHRR passes) seems to go across fronts in the Chl-a distribution, and being more limited by gradients in the SST data. Additionally, it is interesting to notice how the western extension of high pigment concentration to the Northwest of Jutland is increasing during the days 13th to 15th as a result of the strong south easterly winds as well as the bloom being in its growth phase.

5.1.2 Case II: *Chattonella* bloom in April - May 2000

On April 18th 2000 a significant increase in the level of chlorophyll pigment concentration in the SeaWiFS data was reported by the Nansen Center to occur along the south west coast of Jutland (Pettersson et al, 2000). This high concentration of algae was confirmed in the same region two days later by a regular research cruise by Institute of Marine Research with the research vessel G.M. Dannevig. Most of the algae biomass in the region was due to phytoplankton of the class Raphidophyceae. In this class of algae, several harmful species are known, e.g. *Chattonella*, *Fibrocapsa* and *Heterosigma*. Very high concentrations of the algae *Chattonella* aff. *Verruculosa* was reported in the waters west from Esbjerg on April 20. The further development and subsequent decay of the bloom were efficiently monitored using EO and *in situ* data in combination. Due to the extent and rapid development of the algae bloom, the monitoring operations also went into an alert mode. During this period also satellite data were used to initiate and update (using a simple scheme of data assimilation) the model predictions of bloom development, using the IMR research forecasting algae model (NORWECOM). Clear benefits of using EO data were identified with respect to the planning of the monitoring operations, as well as in the model predictions of the development of the algae bloom. Similar algae blooms of *Chattonella* spp. and *Heterosigma* also occurred mainly in the Jutland current in 1998, but these species were in 1998 also observed blooming in Norwegian coastal waters (near Farsund and Flekkefjord, see Chapter 5.1.1). During these events the algae bloom caused the death of a lot of farmed as well as wild fishes.

During the days prior to May 5 a narrow tongue of water with higher pigment concentrations was observed to “break out” from the Jutland current into the central and northern parts of Skagerrak (Figure 9). These waters most likely included the *Chattonella* species and could possibly cause advection of the blooms into the coastal Norwegian waters. Dedicated field investigations were initiated in order to evaluate this observation. Analysis of the field data confirmed the observations in the satellite image, however these water masses did not reach the Norwegian coastal waters to become a treat for the aquaculture industry. The Nansen Center, Plymouth Marine Laboratory, the Institute of Marine Research and the Directorate of Fisheries were able to monitor the development and decay of this and other algae blooms using daily updated satellite images, regular, sporadic and dedicated *in situ* measurements and predictive numerical ecosystem model.

On May 4th the three EO data sources are acquired throughout the day – from a morning SST mapping at 05:54 UTC (as well as the following morning at 04:42), a noon SeaWiFS chlorophyll mapping at 12:19 UTC and an evening ERS SAR pass at 21:30 UTC (Figure 10). This implies that the observations are not synoptic and that the environmental conditions have changed during the time evolution between the different satellites pass. However, similarities in the mapping of the ocean surface are observed in the different EO data sources. The SST data from May 5th at 04:42 UTC (not shown) have been used to supplement the interpretations of the ocean surface signatures. The regionally good weather conditions for visible and IR mapping and the low wind conditions make it possible to observe some interesting common features in the radar and optical images - starting from south going northward:

In the German Bight and off-shore of southern Jutland, very high pigment concentrations are observed in the SeaWiFS image as well as being conformed by *in situ* observations. In some areas the chlorophyll retrieval algorithm for the SeaWiFS data saturates, supporting the fact that the

pigment concentrations are in fact very high (Figure 9 and Figure 10). In some of these areas (but not all) one observes a low radar backscatter signal in the ERS SAR image. Most likely this is due to the very high surface concentrations of algae biomass which is damping the surface capillary waves and causing the reduced radar return signal (see Figure 12 areas C and D). The wind pattern (Figure 11) in this region has changed significantly during the day, when wind speed earlier was up to 8 m/s. In the evening during the ERS SAR pass the wind in the entire swath of images was quite homogeneous and low (2-3 m/s). Hence the impact of the algae biomass on the damping of the surface waves might not be the only reason for the damping the radar backscatter areas observed along west Jutland. During this day there is significant reduction in the wind speed along the coast of west Denmark. At the time of the SeaWiFS passage (at 12.19 UTC) the wind speed was 4-6 m/s in the southern parts of the image. During the SAR mapping about nine hours (21:30 UTC) later the wind had decayed to about 2-3 m/s (Figure 11). In conclusion these wind conditions might have been sufficient to cause the damping of the surface capillary waves as observed in the SAR image (Figure 10 d).

In the central part of the SAR images (around 56°30'N in Figure 10) the radar backscatter signal is more homogeneous and seems to be dominated by wind blowing from Skagerrak (northeast). The wind signature in the SAR image in this region indicates somewhat higher winds than what is reported in the ECMWF data. Unfortunately only LRI data are available from this day and no absolute retrieval of the wind speed is therefore possible from the SAR data.

In the northern part of the SAR image swath (58-57°N), closer to the Norwegian coast (Figure 10) the extension and meandering of the front of the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) around Lista is identified in the NOAA AVHRR sea surface temperature (SST) images, the Chlorophyll pigment concentration (slightly less contrasts, but still gradients observed), as well as in the ERS SAR backscatter resolved as current shear features. The temporal differences in the time of the EO data acquisition resolves also the advection of the fronts with time, however the shapes and extent of current features remains comparable between the different data sets.

Further offshore beyond the location of the NCC front, as well as in a larger region across the SAR image in the central Skagerrak between Denmark and Norway ($\approx 57^{\circ}15'N$), there are two regions of lower backscatter. These regions of low backscatter /surface slicks are not collocated exactly at the areas of highest Chlorophyll concentrations, which is at the tongue of higher pigment concentrations and warmer water of origin from southern Skagerrak north of Hirtshals. This feature is following the 200-meter depth contour superimposed on the SeaWiFS image (Figure 10). This high algae concentration feature was confirmed by dedicated observations performed by the Directorate of Fisheries, based on the satellite observations. South of this feature is another low-backscatter signature in the SAR image which is collocated with the frontal boundary between the water of Skagerrak and Atlantic (North Sea) origin. The system is characterized by (1) the inflow of colder and less chlorophyll rich water as well as (2) the outflow from Skagerrak of warmer and more chlorophyll rich water. A current shear causing convergence is expected in the area, which may cause the SAR signature.

According to the Radarsat image of May 12th at 06 UTC, the wind speed in the region is higher in the near shore and particular the northern parts of the image (Figure 13). This is not exactly consistent with the ECMWF weather map of the wind distribution, however the area of the lowest wind speeds are partly consistent with the lowest backscatter values in the Radarsat image. The areas of damped radar backscatter seems to be confined close to the western boundary of the high biomass extension west of Jutland, again co-located with the boundary between the warmer coastal and the colder off-shore water masses. Assuming a homogeneous air temperature in the region the air masses over the off-shore waters is expected to be more stable than the area closer to land. No particular indications are found that the areas of high damping of the radar backscatter area co-located with particular high biomass. Accordingly it is plausible to conclude that the synergies in the image signatures is found in the region of low wind speed and that the triggering factor is the sea surface temperature and its impact on the stability of the boundary layer. Clear conclusions will require field observations during such events.

Figure 9: AVHRR SST (°C) at 05:54 UTC, ERS-2 SAR backscatter at 21:30 UTC and SeaWiFS Chlorophyll concentration (mg/m³) at 12:19 UTC on May 4th 2000.

Figure 10: Area enhanced selection of the data shown in Figure 9.

Figure 11: ECMWF reanalysis wind fields during the 4th of May (Please notice the different colour scales for the wind speed).

Figure 12: Details of related sea surface features in SAR and SeaWiFS data including the radar backscatter level in each area.

R.Sat.12.May.00 06:00z Denmark W.coast.

Figure 13: Radarsat ScanSAR image (06:00 UTC) with corresponding AVHRR SST image (14:55 UTC). ECMWF wind field from time of Radarsat image (06 UTC) on May 12th, 2000.

5.1.3 Case III: *Chattonella* algal bloom along “Sørlandet” - 25-27 March 2001

Earlier than expected a massive bloom of *Chattonella* occurred in the Norwegian coastal waters along the coast of “Sørlandet” westward to Egersund during the end of March and early April, 2001. The first high concentration (1.1 mill/L) of *Chattonella* was reported in Flødevigen on the 16. March, simultaneously with a report of elevated chlorophyll concentrations in the SeaWiFS images in central Skagerrak and on the 20th March also along large areas of the coast of “Sørlandet”. On the 17th and 18th loss of aquacultured fish was reported in “Gamle Hellesund” and totally 650 tons were lost at this location. Very high cell concentrations, up to 18 mill cells per litre, were reported in Lyngør on the 26th. This algal bloom caused damage along the coast of “Sørlandet” extending westward to Flekkefjord. Favourable north-easterly winds stopped this bloom from being advected westward up along the coast of Jæren and being transported into the region of the major Norwegian aquaculture industry (Rogaland and Hordaland counties). In the satellite data as well as being confirmed by *in situ* observations and model simulations (Figure 17) a major part of the bloom front was trapped in two eddies located south of the Kristiansand-Mandal area and in an area offshore Lista-Flekkefjord (Figures 12-14).

No ERS SAR coverage was available covering these coastal eddies with the very high algae biomass concentrations of *Chattonella*. However, the area further east in central Skagerrak was covered by ERS-2 SAR on the 27th of March southward to the western coast of Jutland. During this period the bloom in this region was in a decaying stage, although still with significant high algae concentrations. The sequence of SeaWiFS pigment distribution during the period May 25th to 27th (Figure 14) indicates a clear decay in the algae bloom activity. Analysis of the wind field, both from the ECMWF and using the CMOD-IFR2 algorithm on the SAR data shows a significant latitude gradient in the wind speed from 1-2 m/s in the northern region in Skagerrak to above 10 m/s in the southern Jutland waters (Figure 16). Accordingly, the wind effect dominates the SAR image signature and no oceanographic induced signal is detectable in the SAR image in this region. In the northern part of the sequence of ERS-2 SAR images on the other hand, the winds are less, but still without very clear evidence of any oceanographic signatures resolved in the image (Figure 15).

Analysing the co-location between surface signals in respectively the SAR and SeaWiFS images for the Skagerrak area reveals some consistency between the gradient contrasts in the chlorophyll pigment distribution and the low backscatter in the SAR images (Figure 14 and Figure 15). The match between the signatures seems however not to be related to concentration but rather induced by local atmospheric and sea surface effects. Accordingly a SAR interpretation of the biological activity without any *in situ* or other EO data on the chlorophyll or pigment distribution seems difficult. Obviously some of the boundaries between the various water masses with different pigment concentrations, SST's and surface roughness (radar backscatter) are co-located in the three different EO data sources. However, the high sensitivity of the radar backscatter to the local wind conditions makes the radar mapping of the ocean features much more sensitive to other environmental (oceanographic and meteorological) conditions than the ocean features directly mapped in the SST and the pigment distribution.

Figure 14: SeaWiFS Chlorophyll concentration for 25th-27th March 2001 and a mosaic of the two ERS-2 SAR scenes.

Figure 15: ERS-2 SAR images overlaid on the SeaWiFS Chlorophyll concentration image from 27th of March 2001.

Figure 16: Wind retrieved from ERS-2 SAR using CMOD-IFR2 and wind direction from image spectra. The wind vectors are overlaid on the SeaWiFS image and can also be compared to the ECMWF wind field (centre panel).

Figure 17: NORWECOM model simulations of the development phytoplankton flagellates for 28th March and 5th April, 2001, based on initiation of the model with the first observations of the *Chattonella* bloom on the 25th.

5.1.4 Case IV: Late spring bloom - May 2001

A general late spring bloom situation occurred again in the Eastern North Sea and Skagerrak region during May 2001. High pigment concentrations along the continental European coastal areas (from the Netherlands to Denmark – see Figure 18, Upper left) and a bloom initiated in the central North Sea was advected towards the western Skagerrak waters. The latter bloom forms a boundary between the lower pigment concentrations in the central North Sea as well as towards the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC - along the coast of Jæren) water with lower algae blooming activities. The high concentration bloom in the central North Sea water is also warmer than the surrounding water masses to the north and south of this region. The colder water in the NCC is most likely due to a period of winds from northwest causing upwelling in the coastal waters.

The SeaWiFS and AVHRR data were acquired during May 9th, while the SAR data acquisitions took place the day before (Figure 18). The miss-match is caused by unfavourable cloud conditions for the AVHRR and SeaWiFS data on the 8th and lack of SAR acquisition on the 9th, accordingly an exact temporal and spatial match between the data and their interpretation is difficult.

The areas of the lowest SAR backscatter values are confined to the areas of the highest gradients as observed in the SeaWiFS pigment concentrations in the south. Further north the lowest backscatter areas are matching the high pigment concentration areas including the maximum gradient areas. In the northern part of the sequence of SAR images the low backscatter occurs in an area of relatively colder and lower pigment concentrations. An exact interpretation cannot be given, however the time difference (advection) as well as the changed environmental conditions between the set of observations may explain some of the discrepancies.

Figure 18: The satellite EO data from 8th and 9th May, 2001. Upper left: The SeaWiFS Chl-a concentration for a larger North Sea region. Upper right: A sub-image of the AVHRR SST coverage. Lower left: The ERS SAR swath. Lower right: A sub-image of the SeaWiFS Chl-a concentration taken from the upper left data set.

5.1.5 Case V: Atlantic frontal zones west of Shetland - May 1999

This is a case with optimal observational conditions for infrared and visible EO sensors with cloud free conditions in most parts of the North Sea region (Figure 19 – upper panels). The pair of AVHRR SST (06:46 UTC) and SeaWiFS (12:12 UTC) images provides valuable information of the different water masses in the region, including the inflow of Atlantic water north west of Shetland, the central North Sea circulation and the coastal currents extensions from continental Europe to Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) along the west coast of southern Norway.

In the area between Shetland and the Faeroe islands the inflow of warm Atlantic waters (the North Atlantic Current) is typically 1°C warmer than the shelf water near the Faeroe Islands, as depicted in the Sea Surface Temperature (SST) derived from the AVHRR data (Figure 19 – upper left). The same Atlantic water masses have moderate biological activity (Figure 19 - upper right), with typical algae chlorophyll-a concentrations between 0.5 and 0.3 mg/m³, significantly lower than the algae blooming water further westward on the banks around the Faeroe Islands, where the Chl-a concentrations are above 2.0 mg/m³, according to the SeaWiFS data. A high correlation in spatial shapes of the ocean features resolved in the two EO data sources is observed, however with an inverse gradient in the two parameters and some geographical displacement probably due to the six hours difference in data acquisition. The absolute difference (contrasts) in the biological phytoplankton bloom activity is larger than the contrast in the SST over spatial scales typically ranging from 5 to 15 nautical miles. The eddy circulation feature observed has opposite spatial gradients in respectively the SST and the Chl-a pigment concentrations. During the same evening an ERS SAR acquisition (22:03 UTC, additionally ten hours later) covered this eddy circulation feature and the current boundary between the warmer and lower biomass Atlantic water and the colder and algae rich areas closer to the Faeroe shelf area. The SAR image also clearly mark the gradient zone and the eddy circulation feature generated at the boundary between these two different water masses – i.e the North Atlantic Current and the Faeroe Island Shelf waters.

A typical late spring (month of May) situation in the NCC is observed, with higher pigment concentrations in the coastal waters and generally less biological activities in the offshore regions (Atlantic/North Sea waters), except for some offshore bloom events. The SST data reveals generally warmer waters in the NCC than further offshore, however the western boundary of the NCC as revealed in the AVHRR SST data are less pronounced than observed in the SeaWiFS Chl-a data. This is due to the diurnal influence of the solar heating, which mask out some of the surface characteristics of the SST in the NCC and the Atlantic waters, while the phytoplankton growth in the NCC water masses are not influenced. Detailed investigations reveal several areas very high spatial correlation between the gradients and features in the SST and the pigment concentrations throughout the NCC. Some spatial displacement can be explained by the six hours temporal difference between the two observations. A clear topographic steering of the westward extension of the NCC by the Norwegian Trench is seen in the Chl-a concentrations (Figure 19 - upper right) where the 200 meters depth contour is superimposed, the same topographically steering is less pronounced in the SST (as discussed above).

The optical (Chl-a) and infrared (SST) EO data reveals a close and direct relation between the physical and biological properties of the ocean circulation and the different waters masses. Both temperature fronts and gradients in the biological phytoplankton activities of the different waters masses are highly spatially correlated. In some areas the relation is direct between high biomass and SST such as in parts of the NCC and in other areas the relation is reversed, such as in the area west of Shetland and in the high bloom areas of the Central North Sea. The rate and range of this correlation is determined by both seasonality (time) and regional characteristics of the water masses. Typically the SST characteristics of the NCC are stronger than the Chl-a during the winter period and reversed during late spring as observed above.

Figure 19: Cloud free conditions during the acquisition of AVHRR (upper left) and SeaWiFS (upper right) data on the 19th of May 1999. The coverage of the ERS SAR image northeast of Shetland is indicated.

6. Summary

The synergetic use of EO SST and chlorophyll pigment concentration observations reveal comparable patterns that are most likely controlled by underlying ocean circulation processes such as frontal meandering, eddies, upwelling and blockage/outbreak of Skagerrak water along the southwest coast of Norway. The correlation of the spatial distribution in SST and chlorophyll are either positive or negative pending on area and season as high biomass areas are either related to colder or warmer water masses. The highest correlations are revealed in the gradient areas between different waters masses, notably coastal water and central Skagerrak and North Sea water.

Both these EO methods are dependent on cloud free conditions. However, whereas the infrared data are available both during day (with to some extent larger uncertainty due to the diurnal solar heating) and night time passages, the ocean colour mapping is limited to day-time passages in the presence of daylight, which of course peaks during the most attractive bloom periods in spring and summer.

In the summer period the algal bloom activity (chlorophyll pigment concentration) and distribution become a better representation of the extension of the Norwegian Coastal Current than the expression in the SST as the SST gradient weakens and may disappear.

In summary joint interpretation of infrared and ocean colour EO data strengthen the analyses and interpretation of coupled physical-biogeochemical activities related to algal blooms, since they provide complementary information on the water masses and ocean circulation features.

Ocean fronts, gradients and circulation features are related to the ocean dynamics which under favourable conditions are also manifested in the SAR images. The surface roughness, typically maintained due to a composite of Bragg waves (resonant with the radar wavelength), the mean square slope (over all wavelengths) and breaking waves modify the interaction of the electromagnetic waves with the surface and in turn the radar backscatter intensity and variability. The surface roughness variability is primarily related to the near surface wind field and the corresponding surface waves in equilibrium with the wind. In addition, the atmospheric boundary layer stability as determined by the difference in SST and air temperature influences the radar backscatter signature in the SAR data via the wind speed adjustment near the surface. However, under moderate to low wind speed (less than 8-10 m/s) also convergence and divergence due to current shear and eddies, and wave damping by surface film of biological or chemical (natural or anthropogenic) origin effect and alter the radar signatures. Hence, such SAR mapping of current features and regions of natural surface film can be correlated to phenomenon observed in the SST and chlorophyll distribution as addressed above.

The constraint in synergetic use of microwave SAR data with the optical and infrared EO observations is associated with temporal separation in the observations primarily due to the high sensitivity of the SAR (at C-band) to the magnitude and rapidly changing near surface wind field.

In view of the above findings and constraints synergetic use of multiple EO observation sensors (SeaWiFS, AVHRR and ERS/Radarsat SAR's) provides relatively few situations where all observations have high quality data covering the same target area within a synoptically acceptable time frame. Furthermore, as the study focused on algae bloom events additional limitation constrain the occurrences of overlapping data coverage (i.e. revisit time and limited swath coverage - in particular the 100 km ERS SAR swath). Such limitations will be significantly reduced with the Envisat satellite in full operation, where the MERIS, AATSR and ASAR sensors are capable of simultaneously mapping the same area of the Earth surface.

It is therefore recommended to request to ESA a dedicated Envisat multi-sensor acquisition of high bit-rate data (MERIS FR and ASAR data) together with AATSR for the study of algal bloom occurrences and distribution during spring 2004. This could be very timely and capitalize on the operational oceanography demonstration

forecasting experiment undertaken as part of the Monitoring of the Norwegian Coastal Zone Environment (MONCOZE) project for the Skagerrak and the North Sea.

It is expected that such a demonstration experiment would clearly document the relative importance of EO and model system in marine monitoring for environment and security. Hence it fits directly within the context of the SatHav program.

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